

A Study on Attributes and Buying Behaviour of Females towards Intimate Apparels

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Abstract:

Lingerie as a product category now boasts a wide product range, with creative advances serving as the industry's backbone. Consumers today have an array of options, ranging from fashion and styling to high end fashion. The fact that women fashion has always been reflected as advancements in society which is undeniable. And, as Indian women reach adulthood, the statement takes on added significance when discussing what they wear. Financial freedom is one of the top concerns for Indian women, particularly in urban areas, and with it comes the opportunity to live a lifestyle that suits one's interests and inclinations. Women enjoy wearing expensive jewellery, carrying high-end electronics, and purchasing clothing and footwear that make them look beautiful, feel comfortable, and express their style statement subtly. When it comes to asking for innerwear or lingerie, the faces that used to be hesitant and 'do not pass your limit' have become less aggressive and more argumentative. Like many Indians who enjoy arguing about anything, Indian ladies now want to discuss their innerwear with persons who can help them get the right things they want. Women used to be at the sole discretion of salesmen who used to pick on the perfect piece of lingerie for them based on size, fit, and brand. The study is concerned with the attitudes, characteristics, and purchasing decisions of young women towards lingerie, as well as its role in today's quickly changing times. A systematic questionnaire is used to collect data from 100 young women between the ages of 18 and 30 years.

Keywords: *attitudes, attributes, Consumer behaviour, lingerie, intimate apparel, sales promotion*

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1. Introduction

The introduction of several major multinational brands into the Indian market in recent years indicates that India has enormous growth potential for the lingerie business. When it comes to purchasing lingerie, Indian women are still highly hesitant. However, they are gradually becoming bolder when it comes to their choice of selecting lingerie and as a result, the Indian scenario of the lingerie market is changing rapidly as one can find the rise of branded national and international lingerie flooding in India. Indian women have become more conscious about their looks because of reasons such as an increase in the number of working women, changing fashion trends, improved knowledge and media exposure, and the influx of well-known multinational companies into the Indian market. Demographic factors like age, education, occupation, income, and city of residence also influence the buying behaviour. Most of researches available on lingerie till date majorly focuses on one factor i.e., the age of consumer depicting their various buying motivations related to body size, shape, and social acceptance because of their intimate apparels [1].

The old practise of storing lingerie in a closet corner is no longer practiced in modern times. Rather, women's taste in undergarments has reached new heights, and it is not overstated to suggest that it has become a fashion statement. A closer look of the reasons behind this transformation points to various trends, the most prominent of which is women's shifting attitude towards their innerwear. There may be several factors which can influence the purchasing decisions of intimates: aesthetic, functional, physical, religious, etc. Out of these, the aesthetic factors play an important role during the process of purchasing intimate [6].

Women's outerwear has changed significantly in recent years, from salwar-kameez and saris to denims, t-shirts, and feminine tops, particularly in urban regions. As a growing number of women join professional lives where they require smart outerwear for the office, parties, and recreation, they choose innerwear that matches the outerwear.

The fitness aspect has fueled sales of sports brassieres and briefs designed for women's athletic activities. Finally, significant occasions such as a wedding or social gatherings necessitate a unique look. The aesthetic aspects involve the colour, style, shape, material, texture, line, form, fitting and finishing of the intimate which denotes the appearance or the attractiveness. Colour is considered as a key issue and obvious noticeable fact at glance in a product [3].

The main objective of the Study were:

1. To study the attitudes of young women towards lingerie and its purpose in today's rapidly changing times.
2. To analyze the factors that influence women's lingerie purchasing decisions.
3. To analyze the most preferred brands of intimate apparel.
4. To study the effect of sales promotion of buying of the intimate apparel

Limitations of the study

1. The study has been done only for women consumers in the age group of 18-30 years.
2. The sample has been taken only from Jaipur.
3. The type of lingerie has been restricted to brassieres and knickers.

2. Material & Methods

Locale of study: The locale of the study was Jaipur.

Selection of method: Close-ended Questionnaire was prepared for collection of data.

Selection of sample: A total of 100 women between the ages of 18 and 30 were approached to complete out the questionnaire and provide information. The samples were chosen at random.

Data collection: Primary data was gathered using questionnaires, and secondary data was gathered through books, journals, magazines, and the internet.

Analysis of data: The questionnaire data was transferred to the coding sheet by assigning numerical values to the responses. This enhances data tabulation and analysis by reflecting the percentage of data.

3. Analysis of Data & Interpretation

Table 1: Family type (n=100)

S. No.	Family type	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1.	Nuclear	62	62%
2.	Joint	38	38%

According to the data presented above, 62% of respondents belong to a nuclear family, while 38% belong to a joint family. As a result, it can be stated that the size of the family has a direct impact on the family's clothes consumption pattern.

Table 2: Monthly income of family (n=100)

S. No.	Monthly income of family (in rupees)	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)
	Up to ₹50000	16	16%
2.	₹50001- ₹75,000	35	35%
3.	₹75001- ₹1,00,000	37	37%
4.	₹1,00,001- ₹1,25,000	12	12%

According to the above table, majority (37%) of the respondent has a monthly income above ₹75001- ₹1,00,000, followed by 35% with an income bracket of ₹50001- ₹75,000, 16% earned up to ₹50000, and the remaining 12% earned up to ₹1,00,001/-1,25,000. As a result, it is assumed that family income plays a major and influential role in purchasing the products.

Table 3: Most preferred intimate apparel by women (n=100)

S. No	Most preferred intimate apparel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Branded	72	72(%)
2.	Non-Branded	28	28(%)

According to the above table, 72% of women preferred branded intimate apparel over 28% who selected non-branded intimate apparel. In conclusion, women today choose branded intimate apparel over non-branded intimate apparel because of the style, fit, and comfort.

Table 4: Preference towards shopping style (n=100)

S. No.	Preferences	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Mass merchandiser	16	16%
2.	Shopping Mall	56	56%
3.	Mono Brand Store	20	20%
4.	Specialized store	30	30%
5.	Online store	38	38%

The above mentioned table reveals that 56% of women went to the shopping malls to purchase intimate apparel, 38% women visit online stores, 30% women go to the specialized store, 20% of women visit the mono branded store and the remaining 16% purchase intimate apparel by mass merchandiser. Hence, it can be concluded that women are more prompt to malls and online store so that they may get a quality and wide range of products under one roof.

Table 5: Preferred Brand for Intimate Apparel (n=100)

S. No.	Branded means	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	H & M	20	20%
2.	Zivame	06	6%
3.	Jockey	42	42%
4.	Enamor	03	3%
5.	Triumph	05	5%
7.	Marks & Spencer	06	06%
8.	Body care	12	12%
9.	Others	06	6%

From the above table, it can be revealed that 42% of women preferred Jockey as intimate apparel which means quality assurance to them, followed by H & M (20%), Body care (12%), Zivame, Mark & Spencer and Others (6%), Triumph (5%) and Enamour (3%). It can be concluded that Jockey is the most favourite intimate apparel among the youth due to the affordability, and durability of the product.

Table 6: Attributes when buying intimate apparel (n=100)

S. No.	Attributes means	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Comfort	88	88%
2.	Fit	80	80%
3.	Colours	58	58%
4.	Style & Design	45	45%
5.	Price	68	68%
6.	Availability of matching lingerie	18	18%

According to the above table, branded means comfort for 88% of women, fit for 80% of women, price for 68% of women, colours for 58% of women, style and design for 45% of women, and availability of matching lingerie for 18% of women. As a result, it can be inferred that comfort and fit play a significant part in brand for women in terms of product longevity.

Table 7: Money spend on average on intimate apparel (n=100)

Sr. No.	Money spend on average for intimate apparel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	₹500- ₹1000	46	46%
2.	₹1000- ₹1500	34	34%
3.	₹1500- ₹2000	18	18%
4.	₹2000- ₹2500	02	2%

The above table shows that the majority (46%) of women spend ₹500- ₹1000, followed by 34% who spend ₹1000- ₹1500, whereas 18% of women spends ₹1500- ₹2000, 2% spends ₹2500- ₹3500 on an average for intimate apparel. The results of this survey showed that family income has a direct impact on purchasing branded intimate apparel.

Table 8: Preferred style of intimate apparel (Bra) (n=100)

S. No.	Preferred style of intimate apparel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Soft cup Bra	54	54%
2.	Sports Bra	12	12%
3.	Push -Up Bra	05	5%
4.	Balconette/ Demi Cup Bra	02	2%
5.	Full Support Bra	16	16%
6.	Underwire Bra	06	6%
7.	Strapless Bra	02	2%
8.	Bralette	03	3%

According to the findings based on the facts presented on above data depicts 54% of the respondents preferred soft cup bra, 16% preferred full support bra, 12% preferred sports bra, 6% underwire bra, 5% push-Up bra, 3% bralette and remaining 2% of the respondents preferred demi cup bra and strapless bra for intimate apparel. This result revealed that most of the women preferred soft cup bra in comparison to others because of the stretchability and level of comfort.

Table 9: Preferred style of intimate apparel (Panties) (n=100)

S. No.	Preferred style of intimate apparel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Boylegs/ Boy shorts	02	2%
2.	Classic brief	34	34%
3.	High Cut	08	8%
4.	Hipsters	24	24%
5.	Bikinis	09	9%
6.	Thongs	02	2%
7.	Seamless	21	21%
8.	G-String	--	--

According to the findings based on the facts presented above shows that 34% of the women preferred classic briefs, 24% preferred hipsters, 21% preferred seamless, 9% bikinis, 8% high cut, and remaining 2% of the respondents preferred boys shorts and thongs for intimate apparel. In accordance with this survey it can inferred that most of the women choose classic briefs in comparison to others because of the ease and comfort level.

Table 10: Preference regarding Fabric of intimate apparel (n=100)

S. No.	Preference regarding the Fabric of intimate apparel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Lace	02	2%
2.	Satin	06	6%
3.	Lycra	28	28%

4.	Cotton	44	44%
5.	Polyester	08	8%
6	Nylon	05	5%
7	Spandex	07	7%

According to the findings based on the facts presented above shows that 44% of the women preferred cotton, 28% preferred lycra, 8% preferred polyester, 7% spandex material 6% satin, 5 % nylon and remaining 2% of the respondents preferred lacey material for intimate apparel. In accordance with the results of this survey, most of the women preferred cotton and lycra material in comparison to others because of the stretchability and level of comfort.

Table 11: Frequency for purchase intimate apparel in a year (n=100)

S. No.	How many times women purchase intimate apparel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Once	10	10%
2.	Twice	52	52%
3.	Thrice	25	25%
4.	More than thrice	13	13%

According to the above table, 52% of women purchased intimate apparel twice per year, 25% purchased three times per year, and 13% purchased more than three times per year. The remaining 10% of women bought intimate wear only once a year. As a result, it can be stated that women purchased personal items more frequently in response to a need.

Table 12: Does sales promotion influence women for intimate apparel (n=100)

S. No.	Sales promotion influence women	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Yes	74	74%
2.	No	26	26%

According to the above table, 74% of females were impacted by sales promotion, while 26% were unaffected by sales marketing techniques. As a result, it can be inferred that most women were impacted by sales promotion since it attracts young consumers to intimate clothing and inspires existing customers to make larger purchases. Buy one get one free promotions are a great way for marketers and manufacturers to clear out their inventory rapidly [3].

Table 13: Sales promotion tools which influences women (n=100)

S. No.	Sales promotion tool	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Coupons	16	16%
2.	Discounts	67	67%
3.	Gift cards	13	13%
4.	Scratch card	02	2%
5.	Buy two get one free	04	4%

According to the above table, most (67%) of the respondents were impacted by discounts, followed by 16% of respondents who were influenced by coupons in sales promotion tools, 13% of respondents who were influenced by free-samples/free gifts. Buy two get one free deals impacted 4% of respondents, while scratch cards affected 2%. From the above data it can be pertained that most of the women were impacted by discounts and eagerly awaited the discount price and attractive plans for the purchase of branded intimate clothing.

Buy one get one free is defined as one of the most used sales promotion tools, in the sense that buy one and get one free for no cost is a technique in which the customer is easily enticed to buy the product because there is no additional cost and it should be more valuable from the customer's perspective, so the customer can't ignore such a great deal. Bonus packages and free supplementary products encourage people to acquire the product since they

have a positive attitude towards such offers, especially if they are in large sizes and adequately publicised. Furthermore, such promos boost product trial and client switching [4]

Table 14: Sales promotional tool affect the behaviour of buying of the intimate apparel (n-100)

S. No.	Effect of sales promotional tool	Frequency	Percentage
1.	A sales promotional tool prompted me to purchase a brand that I do not normally purchase.	16	16%
2.	I normally purchase the same brand even when I have a sales promotional tool for other brands.	46	46%
3	A sales promotion tool prompted me to purchase the product earlier than expected.	20	20%
4.	A sales promotional tool has prompted me to purchase another brand that I do not regularly purchase.	10	10%
5	A sales promotional tool has prompted me to purchase a product that I have never tried before	08	8%

From the table, it can be depicted that majority(46%) of the respondents generally purchase the same brand even when they have a sales promotional tool for other brand, followed by 20% who responded that sales promotional tool has allowed them to buy the product earlier than planned, 16% of the respondents revealed that sales promotional tool has prompted them to purchase another brand that what they do not regularly purchase and 10% quoted sales promotional tool has prompted them to purchase another brand that they do not regularly purchase and 8 % of them quoted that sales promotional tool has encouraged them to purchase a product that they have never used before. It may be stated that most of the females were influenced by sales advertising tools and waited patiently for discounted rates and good schemes for buying goods.

Brand plays a major role in female consumer’s decision-making process. Three points emerged as drivers in process of decision making in retailing. The first one is emotional (Brand), second is service (Outlet atmosphere) and third is experience (consumption and shopping) [2].

4. Conclusion

The consumer behavior of young women towards intimate apparels is influenced by various factors such as brand familiarity, perceived risk, attitudes, purchase intentions, fashion trends, peer influence, quality, comfort and price. Intimate apparels are not only functional but also symbolic of personal identity and self-expression. Therefore, marketers need to understand the preferences and motivations of this segment and design products and strategies that appeal to them.

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